

1 Quantifying the influence of 2D & 3D urban 2 morphology on thermal environment across climatic 3 zones

4 Wanben Wu^a, Zhaowu Yu ^{b*}, Jun Ma^a, Bin Zhao^{*}

5 ^a Ministry of Education Key Laboratory for Biodiversity Science and Ecological Engineering, National
6 Observations

7 and Research Station for Wetland Ecosystems of the Yangtze Estuary, and Shanghai Institute of EcoChongming
8 (SIEC), Fudan University, Shanghai, 200433, China; wbwu19@fudan.edu.cn (Wanben Wu);

9 ma_jun@fudan.edu.cn (Jun Ma)

10 ^b Department of Environmental Science and Engineering, Fudan University, Shanghai, 200433, China

11 * Correspondence: zhaobin@fudan.edu.cn; zhaowu_yu@fudan.edu.cn

12 **Abstract:** Urban heat islands (UHIs) have a significantly negative impact on human health and
13 urban sustainability. Two-dimensional (2D) landscape patterns in UHIs are well documented;
14 however, the effects and contributions of three-dimensional (3D) urban structures remain
15 unclear, especially across different climatic zones. We investigated the relationship between
16 2D/3D urban morphology and the urban thermal environment in summer and winter during the
17 day and at night in 62 representative large cities across four major climate zones in China. First,
18 we extracted the seasonal surface regional heat island intensity (SRHII) using the MODIS 8-
19 Day land surface temperature (LST) product. We then constructed twenty-five 2D and five 3D
20 urban features and explored their relative importance and respective roles for UHIs in different
21 climatic contexts. Results show that: (1) there are significant differences in SRHII between
22 various climate zones; cities with a humid subtropical climate experience temperatures around
23 2 °C higher during the day in summer compared to those in the other climate types. (2) 3D
24 urban features can effectively improve the interpretation of urban features for SRHII, with an
25 average optimization level of 21%. (3) Urban trees have a higher cooling effect than other green
26 spaces, while taller buildings can also reduce the UHI effect. (4) On summer days, equal
27 proportions of tree to building volume provide the greatest cooling benefit. This study provides
28 new insights into the effect of 3D urban characteristics on SRHII and has promising
29 implications for climate resilience planning and heat-related risk management.

30 **Keywords:** surface urban heat island; 3D Urban characteristic; landscape metrics; climate
31 adaptation; climate background

32

33 **1. Introduction**

34 The urban heat island (UHI) is a phenomenon in which urban areas experience higher atmospheric and
35 surface temperatures than the surrounding non-urban areas (Voogt et al. 2003; Rizwan et al. 2008). There
36 is considerable scientific evidence demonstrating that UHIs significantly influence water and air quality,
37 energy consumption, and heat-related diseases (Grimm et al. 2008; Shepherd et al. 2005; Huang and
38 Cadenasso, 2016). Therefore, understanding the mechanisms that enhance (or mitigate) UHIs has
39 become an urgent issue to be addressed, and a clear understanding of the factors that affect UHIs is
40 crucial for reducing their harmful effects (Yu et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2021; Mohajerani et al., 2017).

41 Numerous studies have demonstrated that 2D urban characteristics significantly affect UHI effects. For
42 example, the proportion of impervious surfaces is considered to be highly positively correlated with heat
43 island intensity (Li et al. 2011; Pal et al. 2017; Henits et al. 2017; Yang et al. 2021; Yu et al., 2019),
44 while urban green space is an important land cover which reduces heat island intensity (Gallo et al. 1993;
45 Kikon et al. 2016; Fan et al. 2015; Yusuf et al. 2014). Estoque (2017) proved that the density and
46 aggregation of impervious surfaces, as well as green spaces, have a strong correlation with UHI.
47 Meanwhile, various 2D landscape metrics of impervious surfaces or green spaces, such as edge density
48 (ED) and largest patch index (LPI), have been considered important factors influencing UHIs. All of this
49 highlights the impact of fragmentation of green spaces and building sites on heat island intensity (Huang
50 et al., 2019; Nastran et al., 2019; Jia and Wang, 2020).

51 Compared with 2D models, urban 3D structures reflect real urban characteristics enabling a better
52 understanding of the urban thermal environment pattern and heat transfer process. Therefore, it is
53 particularly urgent to explore how 3D urban characteristics affect the UHI. Previous studies have
54 explored the relationship between 3D urban characteristics and UHIs at the individual city scale (Berger
55 et al., 2017; Hu et al., 2020). Factors such as building height, tree height, height/width ratio, and sky
56 view factor (SVF) are considered to affect heat island intensity in some case studies (Huang et al., 2019;
57 Yu et al, 2020). Specifically, Yu (2020) explored the effect of building and tree height on surface
58 temperature in Shanghai using a high-resolution digital surface model (DSM) and Landsat 8 TIRS images
59 and concluded that high-rise or low-rise buildings were more likely to reduce the UHI effect. By
60 analyzing the relationship between the sky view factor and land surface temperature (LST) in Beijing,
61 Huang (2019) showed that building height can affect the UHI by influencing wind speed and heat
62 emissions. Tian (2019) showed that the height and spacing of buildings affect air circulation and wind
63 flow causing the UHI effect in Beijing.

64 All these studies have contributed to our understanding of the UHI. However, some studies have also
65 argued that 3D urban forms are not as important for the interpretation of the UHI as the 2D urban features
66 (Berger et al., 2017). The main reason for these inconsistencies is that these results cannot be generalized
67 because all the above studies are specific case-based studies at the city or regional scales. Therefore, the
68 real contribution of 3D urban characteristics to the UHI intensity has not yet been explained well. In
69 addition, the UHI effect may vary from region to region, especially because rainfall, humidity, and
70 temperature are significantly correlated with UHIs (Du et al., 2016; Geng et al., 2022; Kim et al., 2018;
71 Zhao et al., 2014); different climatic contexts should be considered when studying the effect of urban

72 characteristics on UHIs or the effect of 2D/3D urban structures on them. Therefore, studies at the
 73 climatic-zone scale are extremely important.

74 To address the aforementioned knowledge gap, this study attempts to answer the following questions:
 75 (1) What are the seasonal, day and night patterns of UHIs under different climatic contexts? (2) To what
 76 extent do 3D urban features contribute to UHIs in different climate zones? (3) How do 2D and 3D urban
 77 features affect the UHI intensity under different climatic conditions? The results of this study enhance
 78 the understanding of the relationship between urban 2D/3D features (especially the contribution of 3D
 79 features) and the UHI effect and can provide an important reference for climate resilience planning at the
 80 climate zone scale.

81 2. Materials

82 2.1 Study Area

83 The distribution of the 62 cities ranged from 91°E-128°E and 18°N-46°N (Fig.1). The study area covers
 84 a total area of 800,533 km² and has a total population of 463 million (36.7% of the total population of
 85 China). In addition, the study cities are mainly distributed in nine different climate zones: Cfa: temperate-
 86 no dry season-hot summer, Dwa: cold-dry winter-hot summer, Cwa: temperate-dry-winter-hot summer,
 87 arid- steppe-cold, Aw: tropical-savannah, Bwk: arid-desert-cold, Cwb: temperate-dry winter-warm
 88 summer, Dwc: cold-dry winter-cold summer, and Dfd: cold-no dry season-very cold winter. For each
 89 city, the global urban boundary (GUB) in 2018 (Li et al., 2020) was used as the boundary of the urban
 90 area.

91

92 **Fig. 1.** Geographic locations of 62 studied cities and climate classification scheme of China. Af: tropical-
 93 rainforest; Am: tropical-monsoon; Aw: tropical-savannah; Bwk: arid-desert-cold; Bsh: arid-steppe-hot;
 94 Bsk: arid- steppe-cold; Cwa: temperate-dry-winter-hot summer; Cwb: temperate-dry winter-warm
 95 summer; Cwc: temperate-dry winter-cold summer; Cfa: temperate-no dry season-hot summer; Cfb:

96 temperate-no dry season-warm summer; Cfc: temperate-no dry season-cold summer; Dsb: cold-dry
97 summer-warm summer; Dsc: cold-dry summer-cold summer; Dwa: cold-dry winter-hot summer; Dwb:
98 cold-dry winter-warm summer; Dwc: cold-dry winter-cold summer; Dfa: cold-no dry season-hot
99 summer; Dfb: cold-no dry season-warm summer; Dfc: cold-no dry season-cold summer; Dfd: cold-no
100 dry season-very cold winter; EF: polar-frost.

101 **2. Data**

102 **2.2 MODIS Land Surface Temperature (LST) Data**

103 MODIS 8-day land surface temperature (LST) data (MOD11A2 product) from 2018 were used to
104 quantify UHI. MOD11A2 can provide daytime LST (approximately 10:30 Ante Meridiem) and night-
105 time LST (approximately 22:30 post-meridiem) at a resolution of 1 km. All MOD11A2 products are
106 freely available from the Google Earth Engine (GEE) data catalog ([https://developers.google.com/earth-
107 engine/datasets/catalog/MODIS_006_MOD11A1](https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/MODIS_006_MOD11A1)).

108 **2.3 Datasets of human settlements**

109 The global **human settlements** product for 2018 at a 10-m resolution was proposed using Sentinel-2
110 data and convolutional neural networks (CNN). Build-up probability values range from 0 to 100, and
111 this study used a threshold of 20 to extract building distributions (Corbane et al., 2021). The building
112 floor data for 2017 were collected by Baidu Map Services, China ([ww.map.baidu.com/](http://www.map.baidu.com/)). It is available
113 for a single building as a polygon, as well as with information on the number of floors for each building
114 (Fig.2 (c)). In this study, we transformed the building floor space into height by multiplying it by three.
115 As evaluated in a previous study, the overall accuracy of the building height product was 86.78% (Liu,
116 et al., 2021).

117 **2.4 Global Forest Height**

118 As one of the important components of the 3D spatial characteristics of cities, tree height may play an
119 important role in the urban thermal environment. This study used the global forest canopy height (GFCH)
120 map for the year 2019 (Potapov et al. 2021), which has a resolution of 30 m, to explore the effects of tree
121 height and tree volume on UHI intensity. The global forest canopy height product was produced with a
122 30 m spatial resolution using Landsat data and Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI)
123 LIDAR-derived vegetation structure data. The global forest height map was compared with GEDI
124 validation data, and it had a high accuracy (RMSE = 6.6 m; MAE = 4.45 m; $R^2 = 0.62$). This global forest
125 map is freely available on the Global Land Analysis and Discovery website
126 (<https://glad.umd.edu/dataset/gedi/>) and is also available from the GEE (Image Collection
127 id: users/potapovpeter/GEDI_V27). The code for calling and analyzing GFCH products in GEE is
128 available upon request. Fig.2 (b) illustrates an example of tree height in Beijing.

129 **2.5 Global Land Cover Map (FROM-GLC10)**

130 Finer Resolution Observation and Monitoring of Global Land Cover for 2017 (FROM-GLC10) was
131 developed using Sentinel-2 images and contains ten land cover categories, including cropland, forest,
132 grassland, shrubland, water, and impervious surfaces (Chen et al., 2019). The overall accuracy is 72.26%.
133 In this study, land cover data was used to calculate the two-dimensional features. FROM-GLC10 can be
134 downloaded free from: [http:// data.ess.tinghua.edu.cn/](http://data.ess.tinghua.edu.cn/). The distribution of buildings and non-built
135 impermeable surfaces (NBIS) was further obtained by combining the built-up area product (introduced

136 in 2.2.3) and FROM-GLC10 product. Vegetation other than trees was cumulatively classified as non-
 137 tree vegetation (NTveg). Fig.2 (a) shows the results of the land use/cover reclassification in Beijing.

138 2.6 Climate classification products

139 The World Map of Köppen–Geiger climate classification products was calculated from observed
 140 temperature and precipitation data for 1980–2016 within a 1 km resolution and used as reference data to
 141 better understand the climate background of the 62 cities (Beck et al. 2018).

142
 143 **Fig. 2.** Land cover, tree height and building height for the case city (Beijing) is presented, (a) integrated
 144 land cover with five types, the global urban boundary (GUB) is the urban boundary defined by the global
 145 urban boundary product, used to define the study area for each city. (b) Tree height product, the blue line
 146 is a 1km × 1km fishing net, the minimum statistical unit for data analysis in this study. (c) A pseudo-3D
 147 display of the Baidu Maps building height product.

148 3. Methods

149 In this study, we first extracted seasonal surface regional heat island intensities (SRHII) using MODIS
 150 land surface temperature (LST) 8-day data. Based on the 10-m-resolution land cover data, building floor
 151 map, and tree height data, a total of thirty 2D/3D urban spatial structure features were constructed. The
 152 influence of urban structural features (both 2D and 3D) on the SRRII of the 62 cities studied was further
 153 explored using a boosted regression tree (BRT) and generalized linear model (GLM).

154 3.1 Methods for SRHII calculation

155 The SRHII was calculated as the difference in surface temperature between each pixel and the
 156 background with few effects of urbanization; the background was determined using land cover, nightlight
 157 intensity, annual maximum NDVI, and digital elevation model (DEM) in previous studies, using the
 158 rules (1)–(5) mentioned below; the effectiveness of these rules was tested in the Yangtze River Delta
 159 urban agglomeration (Chen et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021). In this study, to eliminate UHI differences due
 160 to different climatic backgrounds, we added rule (6), which selects pixels with the same climatic context

161 as the urban area as the background. Finally, the background area was extracted based on the following
 162 rules:

163 (1) The background area was extracted from a 50 km buffer region from the urban area, and in this study,
 164 the global urban boundary (GUB) in 2018 (Li et al., 2020) was utilized as the boundary of the urban area.

165 (2) Areas with night light intensity less than or equal to 15 were considered to be areas not affected by
 166 human activity and excluded.

167 (3) To exclude low vegetation cover areas, including bare land and water bodies, pixels where the
 168 annual maximum NDVI was greater than or equal to 0.6 were considered to represent areas
 169 with high vegetation cover; those with lower values represented low vegetation cover areas
 170 such as bare land and water bodies and were excluded.

171 (4) To reduce the effect of different land cover compositions, only cropland was considered as a
 172 background area.

173 (5) The difference between the DEM and the average elevation of the urban area was assumed to be less
 174 than 50 m to eliminate the temperature difference due to the elevation difference (Anees et al., 2015).

175 (6) Finally, only areas with the same climate type as the specific urban area were considered as
 176 background areas.

177 SRHII is calculated as follows:

$$178 \quad SRHII_i = LST_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{1}^n LST_b$$

179 where $SRHII_i$ is the surface regional heat island intensity of each pixel in the urban area ($^{\circ}C$), LST_i is
 180 the surface temperature of each $1km \times 1km$ MODIS pixel, while $\frac{1}{n} \sum_{1}^n LST_b$ represents the mean LST
 181 of the background area. A positive value of SRHII indicates the UHI effect, while a negative value
 182 indicates a surface urban heat sink.

183 In this study, we calculated daytime and night-time SRHII distributions for Summer (June to August)
 184 and Winter (December to February). The SRHII was calculated using all available 8-day MODIS surface
 185 temperature products from 2015 to 2019. The calculation code in GEE is available upon request.

186 **3.2 Calculation of 2D and 3D urban structure metrics**

187 Thirty 2D or 3D urban metrics were calculated for further analysis (Table 1). For 2D urban landscape
 188 metrics, we first used the FROM-GLC10 product to obtain the distribution of buildings, non-building
 189 impervious surfaces (NBIS), trees, non-tree vegetation (NTVeg), and water using a reclassification
 190 method. Furthermore, we obtained five landscape indices for each category, including total area of class
 191 (CA), largest patch index (LPI), edge density (ED), landscape shape index (LSI), and patch density (PD).
 192 CA was used to represent the area of each class; for example, larger CA values indicate greater coverage
 193 of the corresponding land cover. Large LPI values indicate that the largest category patches are more
 194 dominant in the block area. ED was used to describe the configuration of the landscape; for example,
 195 low ED values indicate an aggregation of the same class. The LSI was used to quantify the complexity
 196 of the class shape; large LSI values indicate more complex class patch shapes. PD was used to quantify
 197 the fragmentation of each class, and grids with large PD values were in the more fragmented category.

198 All the 2D landscape metrics were calculated using package ‘landscapemetrics’ in R version 4.0.2 in a 1
 199 $\times 1$ km grid. For 3D urban structure metrics, mean building height (BH), sum volume of buildings (BV),
 200 mean tree height (TH), total volume of trees (TV), and mean digital elevation model value (DEM) were
 201 calculated for each block, and a total of five urban 3D metrics were obtained. The full names and
 202 calculation methods for the specific indicators are listed in Table 1.

203 **Table 1**
 204 2D and 3D urban structure metrics selected in this study

Urban forms	Name	Calculation method	Range
2D	Area ratio of categories (CA)	$CA = \text{sum}(AREA[patch_{ij}])/A$	$CA > 0$
	Largest patch index (LPI)	$LPI = \frac{\max(a_{ij})}{A} * 100$	$LPI > 0$
	Edge density (ED)	$ED = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m e_{ik}}{A} * 10000$	$ED > 0$
	Landscape shape index (LSI)	$LSI = \frac{e_i}{mine_i}$	$LSI \geq 1$
	Patch density (PD)	$PD = \frac{n_i}{A} * 10000 * 100$	$PD > 0$
3D	Mean building height (BH)	$BH = \text{mean}(BH_i)$	$BH \geq 0$
	Volume of building (BV)	$BV = \text{sum}(VB_i)$	$BV \geq 0$
	Mean tree height (TH)	$TH = \text{mean}(TH_i)$	$TH \geq 0$
	Volume of tree (TV)	$TV = \text{sum}(VT_i)$	$TV \geq 0$

205 $AREA [patch_{ij}]$: area of each patch, e_i : total edge length on cell surfaces; $mine_i$: minimum total edge
 206 length on the cell surface; e_{ik} : total edge length in meters; A : total landscape area in square meters, which
 207 was set as 10^6 m² in this research; n_i : number of patches. Multiple landscape indices were calculated for
 208 the land cover types, including building, non-building impervious surface (NBIS), tree, non-tree
 209 vegetation (NTVeg), and water. The nomenclature of each 2D urban forms is named as “landscape index
 210 land cover type”, i.e., CA_Building represents the area ratio of building in each block.

211 3.3 Statistical Analysis

212 First, the F test in one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) (Lix et al., 1996) was used to determine
 213 whether the SRHII was significantly different among the various climate types. Second, the boosted
 214 regression tree (BRT) model was used to investigate the specific relative importance of each 2D or 3D
 215 urban form metric on SRHII in various seasons (day/night) and climate contexts; this model combines
 216 regression trees and boosting techniques to improve the predictive performance of multiple single models.
 217 The BRT model has been applied in various fields to explore complex and nonlinear relationships
 218 between parameters and can also reduce the risk of overfitting (Friedman et al. 2002). Based on the BRT
 219 model, we evaluated the degree of importance of each variable, based on the BRT model, we evaluated
 220 the degree of importance of each variable; variables with large values of relative importance are the
 221 primary indicators representing the spatial variability of the SUHI. Four parameters need to be defined
 222 in the BRT model: the learning rate (LR), tree complexity (TC), number of trees (NT), and bag fraction
 223 (BF); the final optimal values of LR, TC, NT, and BF were set to 0.001, 5, 1000, and 0.75, respectively.
 224 The BRT model was fitted using the gbm.step function in the dismo package (Elith et al. 2017) with R
 225 (version 4.0.1). To better understand the relationship between 2D/3D urban metrics and SRHII in
 226 different seasons (days and nights) and climate types, a series of generalized GLMs was constructed to

227 assess the relationships between SRHII and various factors; highly related variables (Spearman's $\rho > 0.8$)
 228 were not used in the same model. Akaike's information criterion corrected (AICc) information-theoretic
 229 method was used to evaluate all the models, and the model with the smallest AICc was used. All effective
 230 variables were estimated with a z-value of less than 0.05, which indicated that the variable was
 231 statistically significant. Based on the correlation coefficients (denoted as "slope") of GLM models, we
 232 can discover how each factor relates to the UHI and therefore understand the cooling or warming effect
 233 of that variable. Furthermore, the extent to which the inclusion of 3D features improves the interpretation
 234 of SRHII can be captured by setting up two control groups—2D urban features only and 2D and 3D
 235 urban features—and then constructing a GLM model to interpret SRHII. The R^2 of each GLM model
 236 was used to assess the degree of explanation of all variables for UHI in each group. When performing
 237 statistical analysis, all data from cities with the same climatic context were combined.

238 4. Result

239 4.1 Seasonal and climatic distribution of SRHII

240 The seasonal SRHII during daytime and night-time across all 62 cities is shown in Fig. 3, and Fig. S.1
 241 shows the distribution of the number of cities with different SRHII levels across seasons, days, and
 242 nights. SRHII values were the highest during summer daytime and were mainly distributed between 3
 243 and 4 °C (23 of 62 cities); the mean SRHII was 3.05 °C, and the greatest standard deviation across the
 244 62 cities was 1.41 °C. There were significant differences in SRHII between northern and southern cities.
 245 The mean value of SRHII during winter days was the lowest at 0.25 °C, and the SRHII was mainly
 246 distributed between -1 and 1 °C (38 of 62 cities), but there was a large inter-city variation with a standard
 247 deviation of 1.29 °C, second only to summer days.

248

249 **Fig. 3.** The footprint of surface regional heat island intensity for China's 62 cities during Summer and
 250 Winter, where Mean and SD represent the mean and standard deviation of SRHII for the 62 cities in the
 251 corresponding season/day/night, respectively.

252 The ANOVA F-test ($p < 0.05$) results in Fig.4 indicate that there were significant differences in the
 253 SRHII among the various climate types under all four conditions. Specifically, cities in the Cfa and Cwa
 254 climates have significantly higher SRHIIs during summer and winter days than those in the Dwa and Bsk
 255 climates, while the opposite is true for summer and winter nights, that is, cities in the Dwa and Bsk
 256 climates have a higher SRHII during summer and winter nights than those in Cfa and Cwa climates.

257
 258 **Fig. 4.** SRHII characteristics of the different climate types in (a) Summer days, (b) Summer nights, (c)
 259 Winter days and (d) Winter nights, where the boxes represent the 25th and 75th percentiles, the horizontal
 260 black lines inside the boxes are the medians.

261 **4.2 Relative importance of urban form for SRHII**

262 The relative importance of each variable is given by the BRT model, which can indicate which 2D/3D
 263 urban forms are more important for estimating the SRHII in different seasons or climate types. Fig.5
 264 summarizes the top ten most important variables for each condition. For cities with the Cfa climate type
 265 on summer days, building edge density, building coverage, and volume of tree were the three most
 266 important variables and their total relative importance was 26.8%, 7.1% and 6%, respectively. During
 267 the day in winter, DEM, coverage, and LPI of water were the top three variables in terms of relative
 268 importance (22.7%, 9% and 7.9%, respectively). On summer and winter nights, the volume of buildings
 269 was more important (31.1% and 21.8%, respectively). In Cwa regions, building and tree coverage were
 270 the two most important variables, with relative importance values of 30% and 11%, respectively. During
 271 summer nights, winter days, and winter nights, building coverage and DEM were the two most important
 272 variables. For cities in the Dwa, the relative importance of DEM and tree volume was the highest during
 273 the daytime in both summer and winter; specifically, the relative importance of DEM and tree volume
 274 cumulatively was 49.3% in summer days and 69.8% in winter days. The volume of buildings was the
 275 most important variable on both summer and winter nights, with relative importance values of 34.6%

276 and 36.3%, respectively. For cities in a Bsk climate context, building coverage was the most important
 277 variable on summer days, summer nights and winter nights, with relative importance values of 15.7%,
 278 19.2%, and 22.6%, respectively. According to the BRT results of SRHII under general conditions
 279 (analysis results for all cities), the DEM and impervious surface area coverage (CA_Building or
 280 CA_NBIS) were the two most important variables.

281 In general, 3D urban features have a high relative importance, especially DEM, which ranks in the top
 282 three in almost all scenarios. 3D urban forms such as BV were more important relative to 2D urban forms
 283 in both the Cfa and Dwa climate types and dominated the differences in SRHII at night. Furthermore,
 284 the relative importance values of the same variables showed significant differences between different
 285 climate types.

286

287 **Fig.5.** The ten most important 2D or 3D urban structure metrics related to SRHII based on boosted
 288 regression tree analysis derived mean relative importance values.

289

290 Fig.6 illustrates the contributions of the unique effect of 2D urban metrics, improved explanations of
 291 3D urban morphology, and unexplained variation. The contributions results show that the thirty 2D/3D
 292 parameters of the cities can explain between 13.56% (Dwa, winter days) and 90.51% (Bsk, winter days)
 293 of the SRHII, with an average explanation rate of 44.25%. Furthermore, the addition of 3D urban

294 structures can effectively improve the interpretation of the model, which can be increased by 21.6% from
 295 the original level (using only 2D urban metrics).

296 **Fig.6.** The contributions (expressed as percentage of the total explained variance) of the predictor metrics
 297 of SRHII in four different climate types, the different colors represent three different parts of
 298 contributions, including the unique effect of 2D urban metrics, the improved explanations of 3D urban
 299 morphology, and unexplained variation.
 300

301 4.3 Relationships between urban form metrics and SRHII

302 To further investigate the relationship between the SRHII and the various 2D/3D urban forms, a series
 303 of GLM models of the SRHII and 30 variables were analyzed in different seasons and climate types.
 304 Table 2 illustrates the regression coefficients between the explanatory variables and SRHII. For the 2D
 305 urban form metrics, both land cover composition and configuration have a significant effect on the UHI
 306 in different contexts, with the former having a more significant effect. There was a strong positive
 307 relationship between SRHII and building coverage in both daytime and night-time in different seasons
 308 except in cities in the Dwa region during winter nights; non-building impervious surface coverage has a
 309 warming effect similar to that of building coverage, but with a smaller factor in each model relative to
 310 buildings. In the Cwa climate context, increasing the ED and LPI of buildings can mitigate heat islands.
 311 In contrast, an increase in the ED and LPI of trees promotes heat islands. Tree coverage showed a
 312 significant negative correlation with SRHII and ED_Tree (slope >0 and p <0.05), indicating that a
 313 fragmented distribution of trees may lead to an increase in SRHII. Meanwhile, the relationship between
 314 water coverage and SRHII differed between day and night, as shown by the negative correlation between
 315 water coverage and SRHII during the day and the positive correlation between SRHII at night.

316 For 3D urban form metrics, the results revealed that building height was weakly negatively correlated
 317 with SRHII during the day and night, while building volume demonstrated a significant warming effect
 318 at night and also provided a significant cooling benefit during the winter days in the BSk climate context.

319 Tree height has a complex impact on SRHII, while tree volume shows a completely different effect on
 320 SRHII during the daytime and night-time; specifically, it is negatively related to SRHII in the daytime
 321 but positively related to SRHII at night.

322 **Table 2.** GLM regression coefficients (denoted as “slope”) between 2D/3D urban metrics and SRHII of
 323 various seasons and climate types, R^2 represents the SRHII variation that can be explained by the
 324 regression model. Only variables with statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) and the coefficients for models
 325 with $R^2 > 0.3$ are presented here; to normalize the magnitude of the coefficients, each variable was
 326 multiplied by a factor.

	Cfa		Cwa		Dwa		BSk		Mean									
	Summer	Winter																
	days	nights																
2D Urban Forms																		
<i>Building</i>																		
CA	0.37	0.45	0.50	0.45	0.42	0.18	0.49	0.59	-0.24	8.01	1.58	0.72	0.77	2.33	0.76	0.45	0.34	
ED			-0.22	-0.28	-0.16		0.14		-0.16	0.67	-0.20		-0.35	0.23	-0.11	-0.16	-0.25	
LPI	-0.08	-0.10	-0.13	-0.15	-0.16	-0.13	-0.19		-0.06	-1.95	-0.46			-0.60	-0.24	-0.13	-0.10	
PD							-0.20		-0.14	-1.07				-0.64		-0.05	-0.14	
LSI	0.16	-0.07	-0.12	0.16					0.17					0.16	-0.07		0.02	
<i>NBIS</i>																		
CA	0.45	0.37	0.30	0.22			0.56	0.19	-0.38	4.69	0.84		0.52	1.48	0.47		0.15	
ED	-0.16			0.36	0.48	0.40	-0.45						-0.08	0.48	0.40			
LPI	-0.22	0.56		-0.21		-0.16	-0.29		-0.08				-0.24	0.56	-0.16	-0.08		
PD	0.08	0.08		0.09	0.14		-0.07	-0.08		-0.13	-0.38			-0.07	0.05		-0.13	
LSI	-0.15			-0.27	-0.16	-0.16	0.25		0.11					-0.06	-0.16	-0.16	0.11	
<i>Tree</i>																		
CA	-0.44	-0.35	0.71	-0.59	-0.75	-0.75	0.33		-0.34					-0.23	-0.55	-0.75	0.19	
ED	0.08		-0.16	0.21	0.25	0.25				-0.35			-0.65	0.15	-0.05	0.25	-0.41	
LPI			0.28	0.27	0.19	0.28	-0.24				0.53			0.19	0.19	0.28	0.28	
PD		0.13	0.14		-0.08		-0.54	0.32	0.14					-0.54	0.13		0.14	
LSI	-0.05		0.29	-0.07	-0.08		0.43	-0.07			0.34		0.65	0.11	0.07		0.47	
<i>NTveg</i>																		
CA		0.21	0.24	-0.15	-0.20	-0.19		0.35		-0.56			0.45	-0.15	0.12	0.13	-0.16	
ED	0.07	-0.12	-0.27		-0.12		0.14			0.68				0.30	-0.12	-0.12	-0.27	
LPI	0.47						0.08	-0.08			0.47			0.27	0.20			
PD	-0.09	0.18		-0.09	-0.12					-0.44			-0.15	-0.21	0.18	-0.14		
LSI			0.16	-0.19	-0.24	-0.11			0.08				0.29	0.59	-0.19	-0.24	0.09	
<i>Water</i>																		
CA	-0.27	0.98		-0.18	0.27	-0.54	-0.10	0.79		0.56			0.09	0.00	0.68	-0.23		
ED	0.18		-0.16			0.13		0.12						0.18	0.12	0.13	-0.16	
LPI		-0.38				0.25		-0.36		-0.22			0.15		-0.20	0.25	-0.22	
PD	0.17	0.09		-0.15		0.07					0.15		-0.45	-0.49	0.17	-0.18	0.07	
LSI	-0.10		0.09	0.07			0.13	0.06	0.08		0.55		0.60	0.03	0.30		0.26	
3D Urban Forms																		
BH	-0.03	-0.09	-0.05	-0.12	-0.07	-0.12	-0.05	-0.20	-0.22	-0.41		0.18	-0.21	-0.16	-0.12	0.03	-0.16	
BV		0.14	0.35	-0.04	0.34	-0.10	-0.06	0.43	0.35			-0.22	0.28	-0.05	0.30	-0.16	0.33	
TH	0.11		-0.37	-0.06	0.28		-0.19	0.07	0.06					-0.05	0.07	0.28	-0.15	
TV	-0.20		0.56	0.20	0.53	-0.33	-0.47	0.44	0.06	-0.51				-0.25	0.49	-0.33	0.31	
DEM		0.22	-0.19	-0.10	-0.12		0.09					-0.61	-0.49	-0.32	0.00	-0.17	-0.49	
R^2	0.34	0.36	0.25	0.32	0.47	0.48	0.51	0.29	0.40	0.58	0.24	0.55	0.66	0.90	0.95	0.83	0.47	0.58
Adjusted R^2	0.34	0.36	0.24	0.32	0.47	0.47	0.50	0.29	0.39	0.58	0.23	0.55	0.57	0.88	0.95	0.79	0.44	0.57
<i>slope</i>			-1					0										1

327 To further explore the effects of 2D/3D impervious surfaces and vegetation on SRHII, scatter plots of
 328 impervious surface coverage (ISC, sum of CA_Building and CA_NBIS), vegetation coverage (VegC,
 329 sum of CA_Tree and CA_NTveg), and the ratio of the two to summer daytime heat island intensity were
 330 plotted. Scatter plots of building volume (BV), tree volume (TV), and the coefficient of the two to
 331 summer heat island intensity were also plotted (Fig. 7). The results showed that VegC had a significant
 332 negative linear correlation with SRHII, while ISC had a significant positive linear correlation with
 333 SRHII. Like the negative non-linear correlation between TV and SRHII, the relationship between BV
 334 and SRHII was also non-linear, showing a warming effect first as the building volume increased and then
 335 showing a leveling and constant trend. The scatter plot distributions of the ratio of vegetation to
 336 impervious surface (VegC/ISC) to SRHII and the ratio of tree volume to building volume (TV/BV) to
 337 SRHII showed similar non-linear trends; both were negatively correlated and then smoothly constant.
 338 The VegC/ISC value of approximately 2.5 reaches a smooth trend, while the fitted curve reaches a
 339 smooth trend with a TV/BV of approximately one.
 340

341
 342 **Fig.7.** Scatter plots of multiple variables versus SRHII during the summer daytime, the blue line shows
 343 the smoothed fit trend of scatter plot using “stat_smooth” function in R. Where VegC represents
 344 vegetation coverage (sum of CA_Tree and CA_NTveg) and ISC represents impervious surface coverage
 345 (sum of CA_Building and CA_NBIS).

346 5. Discussion

347 5.1 Impacts of 2D and 3D urban forms on SRHII

348 The results of this study indicate that urban forms, including 2D and 3D, and climate types play an
 349 important role in the SRHII in urban areas. For the 2D urban forms, vegetation and impervious surface
 350 patterns remained the most significant factors influencing SRHII, with high densities of impervious
 351 surfaces as well as low vegetation cover promoting heat islands, which is in line with previous studies
 352 (Li et al. 2012; Chen et al. 2014; Yao et al. 2020; Meng et al. 2018, Peng et al. 2016, and Yue et al.
 353 2019). While water bodies can reduce the heat island during the day, they can enhance the intensity of
 354 the heat island at night; the diurnal differences in the effects of water on UHIs are also demonstrated in
 355 different climate types (Nakayama et al. 2011; Hathway et al. 2012; Steeneveld et al. 2014; Tiangco et
 356 al., 2008; Yu et al., 2020). With the help of the richer land cover information used in the study, the results
 357 show that building cover has a higher warming effect than other impervious surface covers, and tree
 358 cover shows a higher cooling effect compared to other types of vegetation. This may be because trees
 359 can provide both shade and transpiration to achieve cooling. In addition, landscape patterns also have an
 360 important influence on UHI intensity; highly fragmented buildings are effective in cooling, whereas
 361 scattered trees can provide better cooling benefits when the area is a certain size. These phenomena may
 362 be explained by the effect of building and trees on urban ventilation, and it is also possible that
 363 fragmented buildings can generate more shadows. Furthermore, the relative importance of the same
 364 feature for explaining the UHI varies significantly across climatic regions. For example, in the Cfa
 365 climatic region, ED_Building has the greatest relative importance for summer daytime heat islands,

366 which may be due to two factors: First, the increase in ED_Building may increase the shade provided by
367 the building and increase the building-vegetation interface (e.g., trees and grass), which may facilitate
368 the reduction of the heat island through shading effects and convective heat. Second, in Cfa climate
369 zones, high ED_Building can lead to a greater fragmentation of vegetation due to the relatively high
370 urban green space cover; this affects vegetation canopy density and evapotranspiration efficiency, and
371 thus the heat island effect.

372 3D urban features can better reflect the real impact of urban structures on heat. Previous studies
373 have also investigated the role of 3D urban features, such as building volume, SVF, etcetera on
374 temperature (Chen et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2019). According to the urban surface energy balance
375 equation (Oke et al., 2017; Firozjahi et al., 2020), satellite-derived LST is a function of various heat
376 fluxes, such as net radiation, latent heat, sensible heat, and surface and anthropogenic heat fluxes.
377 Therefore, larger trees produce shading and transpiration effects, which can reduce the net radiation and
378 latent heat, and therefore induce a significant cooling effect. The effect of building height on SRHII
379 manifests in two main ways: first, through the heating of the building surface, and second, through the
380 cooling effect of the shading of the building (Li et al., 2011; Oke et al., 2017). High-rise buildings cast
381 more shadows and generate turbulence by increasing the surface roughness, thus achieving a cooling
382 effect (Li et al., 2021); this is consistent with the conclusions of Zhao (2014). In our study, SRHII was
383 negatively correlated with tree size during the day in summer because larger trees produce both shading
384 and transpiration, and thus better cooling. In contrast to previous studies that have concluded that tall
385 buildings have only cooling (Zheng et al., 2019) or warming effects (Guo et al., 2016), the results of this
386 study show that as the building volume increases, it first shows a warming effect and then has little effect
387 on the thermal environment (Fig.7), which is more in line with the urban energy balance; that is, as the
388 building volume grows, the heat island is enhanced by the dominant effect of heat radiation from the
389 walls, but as the building volume continues to increase, the warming effect of the building is balanced
390 by the cooling effect of the shadows it generates. For DEM, elevation showed a significant negative
391 correlation with SRHII; these results are like those obtained in studies on the impact of elevation on
392 SUHII (Li et al. 2017; Wang et al. 2018). The above results show that the 3D characteristics of a city
393 cannot be ignored when implementing heat island mitigation solutions.

394 ***5.2 Implications for UHI mitigation at the climate scale***

395 The relative importance of the same indicator varies significantly between climate zones; for
396 example, the effect of water area on UHIs is more significant in the Cfa climate context than in others.
397 The effect of trees on heat islands is more significant in the Cwa climate than in other climatic contexts.
398 In both the Cfa and Dwa climate zones, BV significantly influences heat island intensity at night, while
399 in both the Cwa and Bsk climate types, building area is the most important factor affecting summer heat
400 island intensity. The above results indicate that neither the 3D characteristics of the city nor the local
401 climatic conditions can be ignored when implementing heat island mitigation solutions. This study shows
402 significant differences in the UHI between different climatic zones. For the subtropical warm and humid
403 climate (Cfa, Cwa), the warm and humid climatic conditions result in dense vegetation in rural areas,
404 thus increasing the roughness of the rural areas, leading to a higher urban temperatures and less efficient
405 diffusion of sensible heat, which leads to a higher heat island intensity. In contrast, in relatively arid

406 climatic zones (Dwa, Bsk), the vegetation type in rural areas is mainly scrub; thus, urban land is rougher
407 than rural land, has a higher convective efficiency, and thus has a relatively lower UHI. While previous
408 studies have focused more on seasonal or day/night differences in UHI (Taheri et al. 2016; Haashemi et
409 al. 2016; Li et al. 2011; Deilami et al. 2018), the results of this study suggest that the climatic context of
410 the city also needs further attention in future studies. Based on the findings of this study, we propose the
411 following recommendations for reducing UHI:

412 (1) When planning new green spaces, trees should be given priority over other types of green spaces,
413 such as grass and flower beds, because trees have a greater cooling effect. (2) It is important to consider
414 how building and tree configurations may affect the UHI. For example, enlarging the distance between
415 buildings and maintaining the integrity of green space can reduce the UHI effect. (3) Considering the
416 cooling effect of high-rise buildings, it is possible to allocate more blue-green spaces to low-rise
417 buildings to reduce the UHI. (4) The area and volume ratio of grey-to-green facilities need to be
418 considered, and green space is allocated in a reasonable manner to improve the overall cooling efficiency.
419 (5) Climate resilience planning requires the consideration of regional climatic conditions and tailoring to
420 local conditions.

421 **5.3 Limitations and future directions**

422 This study has some limitations. First, we focused on the remote sensing-based SRHII, while the
423 canopy layer heat island (CLHI) was also important to the urban thermal environment, which may be
424 more directly and significantly influenced by the three-dimensional structure of the city. However, due
425 to the lack of higher resolution temperature grid data or weather station network data, this study did not
426 cover this aspect, and this issue should be focused on in subsequent studies. In addition, satellite-based
427 daytime and night-time heat islands are transient and hardly reflect the cumulative energy balance
428 throughout the day, which brings a great deal of uncertainty in exploring the effect of 2D or 3D urban
429 features on UHI intensity. Continuous observations by UAV can later be used to compensate for this
430 deficiency. The multiple sources of data used in this study may also have resulted in uncertainty. For
431 example, there may be a deviation between building heights estimated by the floor data and the actual
432 building heights and differences in the year of acquisition for different products (even though the data
433 spans 2017-2019). These may lead to uncertainty in the results due to changes in urban land use/cover.
434 Moreover, to fit the resolution of the MODIS surface temperature, all data were resampled to make
435 their spatial resolution 1km, future studies should consider combining multi-source data (such as
436 Landsat satellite data and UAV data) to explore the effects of 2D/3D urban features on heat island
437 intensity at different scales.

438 **6. Conclusions**

439 The main objective of this study was to investigate the effects of different climatic contexts, seasons,
440 day and night, and 2D and 3D urban structures on UHI intensity. To achieve this objective, this study
441 used high temporal resolution MODIS surface temperature data and improved the algorithm for SRHII
442 to account for SRHII during summers and winters and during day and night for 62 cities (mainly located
443 in four different climate regions) in China. The study further constructed 25 indicators for characterizing
444 2D urban features using 10-m-resolution land cover products and landscape index algorithms along with

445 five urban 3D features using DEM, building height data, and tree height products. The BRT and GLM
446 models were also used to analyze the relative importance, explanatory power, and relevance of each
447 variable. The results of the study fully demonstrate the significant differences in UHIs across different
448 climate types and the non-negligible role of 3D urban features on UHI intensity. Finally, this study also
449 attempts to provide an optimal configuration of grey and green facilities for daytime cooling benefits in
450 summer. The main contribution of this study is that it helps further understand the mechanisms by which
451 2D and 3D urban structures affect heat island intensity and the differences in their effects under different
452 climatic contexts. Multi-source remote sensing data and Earth observation big data were used for this
453 purpose. This study provides new insights into the effect of 3D urban characteristics on SUHII and has
454 promising implications for climate resilience planning and heat-related risk management.

455

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464

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637 **Supplementary Information**

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Supplementary Fig. S2. The number of cities with different level of mean SRHII in urban area

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